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CRITICAL UNDERSTANDING OF TAMAKA SHWASA (BRONCHIAL ASTHMA) AND AYURVEDIC DRUGS IN THE CHILDREN

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Abstract

Background: Asthma is a major noncommunicable disease (NCD), affecting both children and adults, and is the most common chronic disease among children. Asthma affected an estimated 262 million people in 2019 (1) and caused 4,55,000 deaths. Asthma is often under-diagnosed and under-treated, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.

Aim: To understand bronchial asthma in terms of Ayurveda, its causative factors, pathogenesis and treatment modalities & the single drugs available for promotion of healthy life style in *Tamaka Shwasa*.

Materials and methods: This review was done by compiling the classical Ayurvedic literature, Ayurvedic pediatric books as well as PUBMED, MEDLINE database. Based on the collected information, logical interpretation done to review efficacy and mode of action of Vamana, Virechana, Herbal and herbo Minerals drug in the management of Tamaka shwasa

Results & discussion: In Tamak Shwas, the vitiated *Vayu in Prana vaha* srotas when bring up the already vitiated *kapha* from the chest, fails to move freely is blocked by such *kapha* & produces *Shwasa* and its sign & symptoms, pathogenesis, prognosis and treatment can be correlated with Bronchial asthma. The prevalence of respiratory disorders like Tamaka Shwasa (Bronchial asthma) is now a day's increasing alarmingly. The goal of Ayurvedic intervention is not only to achieve control of the disease, it is to improve the quality of life.

Conclusion: The present review helps to understand the disease of the modern era by the Ayurvedic point of view and contributes in the integrative approach in the management of *Tamaka Shwasa* or bronchial asthma

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INTRODUCTION:

Asthma is a chronic disorder of the bronchial tree, characterized by completely or partially reversible airway obstruction which may improve spontaneously or may subside only after specific therapy. Airway hyper-responsiveness is defined as the narrowing of the airway as response to a variety of stimuli i.e allergens, nonspecific triggers and infections. Asthma is a chronic disorder of both children and adults with 300 million individual's afflicted worldwide¹.

Asthma symptoms include recurrent wheezing, coughing, chest tightness, and dyspnea, with nightly and early morning symptoms being more prevalent, whereby quality of life is often reduced². Asthma is one of the most common chronic non communicable diseases currently affecting a large mass of people with almost worldwide distribution³. It is well co-related with bronchial asthma which results due to derangement of *Pranavah Srotasa* (respiratory system) in which *Prana Vayu* is vitiated that is unable to perform its normal physiologic function due to obstruction through cough and moves in upward direction (*Pratilom Gati*)⁴.

Epidemiology:

Asthma is a major noncommunicable disease (NCD), affecting both children and adults, and is the most common chronic disease among children. Asthma affected an estimated 262 million people in 2019 (1) and caused 4, 55,000 deaths. Asthma is often under-diagnosed and under-treated, particularly in low- and middle-income countries⁵.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand bronchial asthma in terms of Ayurveda.
2. To review causative factors, pathogenesis and treatment modalities of *Tamaka Shwasa*.
3. To review the single drugs available for promotion of healthy life style of *Tamaka Shwasa*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This review was done by compiling the classical Ayurvedic literature, Ayurvedic pediatric books as well as PUBMED, MEDLINE database. Based on the collected information, logical interpretation done to review efficacy and mode of action of Vamana, Virechana, Herbal and herbo Minerals drug in the management of Tamakashwasa.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Tamaka Swasa:

Ayurveda has described five types of *Shwasa Roga* and *Tamaka Shwasa* is one amongst them. *Tamaka Shwasa* is a *Vyadhi* i.e., independent disease entity and having its own etiology, patho-physiology and management. *Shwasa Roga* has been considered as a *Yapya Vyadhi* (palliative)⁶.

Tamaka Shwasa is one of the five types of disease *Shwasa*. It is mainly a disease of *Pranavahasrotas*⁷.

The vitiated *Vayu in Prana vaha* srotas when bring up the already vitiated *kapha* from the chest, fails to move freely is blocked by such *kapha* & produces either *Hikka or Shwasa*. It is said that each such effort in *Hikka or Shwasa* originates from *Naabhi (Pittasthana)* just probably to impart the idea of involvement of the extra respiratory muscles of abdomen & neck⁸

The *Tamak Shwasa* arises as an allergic manifestation usually to *Ajeerna* & is associated with *Peenas* & the patient prefers orthopnoeic position. The allergy may be due to any substance or usually starts on a cloudy day. When there is associated fever it is called *Pratamak Shwasa*.

Pradurbhuta Lakshana i.e. clinical features which appear during full manifestation of a disease are called *Rupa or Linga*. They appear during "*Vyaktavastha*" stage of *Shadkriyakala* which is the 5th phase of treating a disease.⁹

Types of *Tamaka Shwasa*

Charaka has mentioned two-allied condition of *Tamaka Shwasa* known as two types or further complication of disease proper i.e., *Pratamaka* and *Santamaka*. *Sushruta* and *Vagbhata* have only mentioned the name as *Pratamaka*, which includes clinical manifestation of *Santamaka*¹⁰.

Pratamaka Shwasa

When Patients suffering from *Tamaka Shwasa* gets afflicted with fever and fainting, the condition is called as *Pratamaka Shwasa*. It is suggestive of involvement of *Pittadosha* in *Pratamaka Shwasa*. It is aggravated by *Udavarta*, Dust, Indigestion, Humidity (*Kleda*), suppression of natural urges, *Tamoguna*, Darkness and gets alleviated instantaneously by cooling regimens¹¹.

As a matter of fact, cooling regimen is one of the causative factors of *Tamaka Shwasa* but in *Pratamaka Shwasa*, the patient gets relief by administering cooling agents due to *Pitta Dosha* involvement.

Santamaka Shwasa

When the patients of *Pratamaka Shwasa* feels submerged in darkness, the condition is called as *Santamaka Shwasa*.

Though *Chakrapani* has mentioned these two as synonyms of each other *Charaka* refers them as two different ailments representing two different conditions of *Tamaka Shwasa*, these two conditions differ from each other according to intensity of attack¹².

Samprapti Ghataka¹³:

- *Dosha* : *Kapha and Vata*
- *Dushya* : *Rasa*
- *Srotas* : *Pranavaha*
Udakvaha
Annavaha
- *Adhistana* : *Urah Pradesh*
- *Srota dusti* : *Sangha*
Vimarga gamana
- *Udbhava sthana* : *Amasaya*
- *Swbhava* : *Chirakari*
- *Roga Marga* : *Abhyantara*

Pathogenesis of Bronchial Asthma¹⁴:

The specific causative factors responsible for the genesis of asthma may produce it by satisfying two conditions. Firstly, they should vitiate upper G.I.T. region, as a result from simultaneous aggravation of kapha and vata in upper G.I.T. & secondly they should produce obstruction to the different channel of circulation, which meant for nourishment, particularly to respiratory system. The pathogenesis occurs finally by two consequent steps. First, which responsible for development of predisposition of bronchial hyperresponsiveness & second which responsible for generation of acute exacerbation.

Step-1: The vata present in respiratory region get aggravate due to aggravation of kapha & vata in upper G.I.T. region. According to classical terms, vata is a set of all inductees liable for catabolism, may beneficial or malicious depend upon condition either balanced (physiological) or unbalanced (pathological) respectively. Here aggravated vata may produce over catabolic state in respiratory region, particularly to bronchus parts. Simultaneously blockage of different channel of nourishment may have a role in induction of malnourishment to the tissues of respiratory systems, particularly bronchial epithelial. Finally it gives way to critical, uncommon and undesirable adaptation of bronchial epithelial. Thus, aggravated vata (appear as a sign of damaged mucosa) prepare a ground for bronchial hyperresponsiveness, which can trigger acute exacerbation justified by consequence step.

Step-2: When patient having bronchial hyperresponsiveness, if get higher aggravation of vata & kapha acute exacerbation can occur. Suggestive causative factors above described same as step-1 also became responsible for this high aggravation. This leads to excessive mucous production by damaged epithelium & bronchus constriction that end into acute exacerbation. The reoccurrence and severity of

bronchial asthma then depend widely on exposure towards causative factors by subject. Status of terminal curability also decided on this exposure and aggravation according to Ayurveda

Purvarupa of Tamaka Shwasa:

Symptom	C.S. ¹⁵	S.S. ¹⁶	A.S ¹⁷
Anaha	+	+	+
Bhakt Dwesa	-	+	-
Adhmana	-	-	-
Arati	-	+	-
Parshwa Shoola	+	+	+
Peedanam Hridaayasya	+	+	+
Vadan vairasa	-	+	-
Shankh bhed	-	-	+
Pran vilomta	-	-	+

Signs and symptoms¹⁸:

- Breathlessness along with forcible expiration
- Cough
- Wheezing
- Tightness of chest
- Thick mucus sputum
- Aggravation of above symptoms during night and early morning
- Fainting during the bout of cough.
- Sleeplessness, discomfort increases when lied down on bed
- Gets comfort in sitting posture.
- Sweating on the forehead.

Tamaka swasa is of two types namely Pratamaka swasa associated with fever, fainting, distention of abdomen and indigestion. Santamaka swasa is pacified by taking of cold regimen

Diagnostic tests in Bronchial Asthma¹⁸:

- Pulmonary function tests include Spirometry and peak flow which estimate the narrowing of the bronchial tubes and how fast an individual can breathe.
- Chest X-ray is useful in differentiating the asthma from other lung diseases.
- Allergy tests helpful in finding the allergen causing the asthma.
- Methacoline challenge test and Nitric oxide tests are confirmatory tests in Bronchial asthma.

Principle of Treatment – Chikitsa Sutra

In Ayurvedic texts, the approach of treatment is based on below mentioned consideration:

◆ Nidan Parivarjana

Acharya Sushruta has explained in *Netar Roga* that avoids the *Hetu* of the disease because prevention is better than cure. The removal of the causative factors leads to the cure of the disease. Change the climate, which is responsible for allergic disease in the body is also a sort of *Nidan Parivarjana*¹⁹.

For *Ayurveda Panchamahabhuta* theory is important as medicinal chemistry for modern medicine. *Charaka* has concluded that all *Dravyas* in the universe are composed of *Panchamahabhuta*.²⁰

◇ Samsodhana

Acharya Charaka emphasized that if there is dominance of Kapha and Vata dosha then patient should be treated with Samsodhana Chikitsa viz. Vamana and Virechana as per requirement and need of the patient²¹ (*Charaka Samhita Chikitsa Sathana (C.S.Ci.) 17/89*). But as per Acharya Yogaratnakar has explained that all procedures of Sodhana Chikitsa shall be adopted except Sneha Basti²² (*Yoga Ratnakar Swasth. Chikitsa 1*).

○ Snehana

Taila mixed with Lavana should be gently massaged on the chest to loose the adhered sputum in the airway²³. (*Charaka Samhita Chikitsa Sathana 17/71*)

○ Swedana

If Kapha thickened in the srotas and obstruct the movement of Vata then by swedan karma movement of vata can be restored in the body srotas²⁴. (*Charaka Samhita Chikitsa Sathana 17/71-72*)

○ Vamana

To eliminate out the kapha (sputum) from the body, vamana should be given with precaution to avoid vitiation of vata dosh. After removal of sticky kapha, the srotas are purified and vata move in that srotas without any obstruction²⁵. (*Charaka Samhita Chikitsa Sathana 17/74-76*)

○ Dhumapana

After vaman therapy the dosha which are still adhered shall be eliminated by the karma²⁶. (*Charaka Samhita Chikitsa Sathana 17/77*)

○ Virechana

The process of eliminating waste products viz. mala and dosa from Adhobhaga of the body is called as virechana karma. Though all virechana dravyas are Panchabhautika in nature but Jala and Prithvi Mahabhuta are dominating in virechana dravyas. As per Acharya Charaka an ideal Virechana dravyas have properties i.e vyavayi, vikasi, suksma, ushna and tikshna²⁷. (*Charaka Samhita Kalpa Sathana 1/4-5*)

◇ Samsamana Chikitsa

Samsamana Chikitsa is very useful and widely accepted by all the patients of all age group. Moreover it is applicable on all the patient who are not eligible for samsodhana chikitsa. Samsodhana Chikitsa includes Deepana, Pachana, kapha Vatasamaka drugs (dravyas) and drugs/dravyas which acts on Pranavaha Srotas as:

Haridra- Classical Reference

Powder of Haridra impregnated with vasa juice & taken with upper fatty layer of milk control the dry cough & swasa²⁸.

The patient should inhale smoke of the wick made of Haridra patra, eranda root, devadaru etc in *hikka & shwasa roga*²⁹.

Haridra powder put in saline water for twenty one days & then parched on fire should be kept in mouth. It control *Hikka, Shwasa & Kapha roga*³⁰. Aromatic oil, turmeric oil, composed of terpene hydrocarbon derivatives and sesquiterpene ketone has also been isolated³¹. (*The Wealth of India P.402*)

Haridra- Anti-asthmatic activity

Research studies have shown Haridra is effective in treating bronchial asthma. Curcumin showed preventive effects on tracheal responsiveness and lung pathological features in asthmatic rats³².

Curcumin significantly ameliorated allergic asthma. The anti-asthmatic effect might be attributed to the suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and elevation of aquaporin expression levels, suggesting further studies and clinical trials to establish its candidature in the treatment of allergic asthma.³³

Draksha: Classical References

Draksa fifty in number, pippali thirty & sarkara one pala (40gm.) should be mixed together with honey & taken³⁴.

Draksha- Brochodilatory Activity

Seed extract of vitis vinifera act as antioxidant, hypotensive, hypolipidemic & vasodilatory effects. Now it was investigated that the effect of grape leaf hydroalcoholic extract act as vasorelaxatory on isolated rat aorta by reducing the tracheal contractions induced by KCL & acetylcholine³⁵. (Mohammad Kazem et al 2005)

Shati - Classical reference

Powder of shati, pushkaramula and amala in equal amount and licked it with honey it is able to cures shwasa and *Hikka*⁶⁷.

Shatyadi churna has used in the management of *Shwasa*³⁷.

Powder of shati, shunthi, shughandhbala in equal quantity and mixed with ghee, this is useful in *Vataj kasa*³⁸.

Shati, pushkarmool, bharangi, guduchi and sunthi etc. in the form of yavagu or decoction, has good effect in *Shwasa*, *Hikka* and *Parshwashula*³⁹.

Shati - Anti asthmatic activity

The powdered rhizome given in divided doses of 10gm to 25 patients with recurrent paroxysmal attacks of dyspnoea for 4 weeks (Bronchial asthma), completely relieved dyspnoea, cough and restlessness in all patients. The ronchi completely disappeared in 36% of the patients. The mean R/R was reduced by 25% and the vital capacity increased by 20%. The mean absolute count also decreased by 55.6%⁴⁰. (Chaturvedi GN, et al 1975)

PIPPALI: Kasa⁴¹, Shwasa⁴², Hikka⁴³

Classical reference: Puran ghrita (old ghee), pippali, kulatthi rasa jangli mansa rasa, sura or (wine), kanji, hingu, draksa, amlaka & bilva etc are useful in *Shwasa & Hikka*⁴⁴ Pippali Churan with Ambala rasa when mix with madhu immediately relief *Hikka*. Similarly act the juices of amalaki & kapitha mixed with pippali & Honey.⁴⁵ Pippali powder 10 gm. Fried in oil & mixed with guda should be dissolved in Kulatha water & given to the patient. It can relieve spasm of cough caused by kapha.⁴⁶

Madhulika (Eleusine carocana), Tugakshii (curcuma angustifolia), Sunthi and Pippali are cooked in ghee and made into Utkarika (a semisolid dietary preparation). It is efficacious in bronchial asthma associated with Pitta⁴⁷.

Effect on respiratory system

Piperine effectively treats asthma is based on a reduction of Th2 cytokines (interleukin-4, interleukin-5), eosinophil infiltration, and by marked reduction of thymus and activation regulated chemokine, eotaxin-2 and interleukin-13 mRNA expression (especially transcription of nuclear factor-kappaB dependent genes) in lung tissue, as well as reduced interleukin-4, interleukin-5 and eotaxin levels in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid, and histamine and ovalbumin-specific immunoglobulin E production in serum⁴⁸

Stimulation of Respiratory System

Petroleum ether extract of *P.longum* produced respiratory stimulation in smaller dose but higher dose cause convulsion in laboratory animals. This may be due to presence of some medullary stimulant factors in the extract⁴⁹ (Kulshresta VK et al 1969).

Bronchodilator

Piper longum has been shown to reduce the passive cutaneous anaphylaxis in rats and protect guinea pigs against antigen-induced bronchospasm⁵⁰ (Dahanukar SA et al 1984). An extract of fruits in

milk reduced passive cutaneous anaphylaxis in rats & protected guinea pigs against antigen-induced bronchospasm⁵¹ (Kulshresta VK et al 1969).

Maricha – Classical reference it is used in Kasa⁵², Shwasa⁵³

Ayurvedic Pharmacodynamic properties, it is used traditionally in the treatment of many various conditions, including respiratory complaints such as asthma, heart complaints, diabetes, colic, worms, haemorrhoids, eczema, intermittent fevers and dysentery⁵⁴. (Sivarajan VV. et.al, 1994)

Relevant Classical reference

Puran ghrita (old ghee), pippali, kulatthi rasa jangli mansa rasa, sura or (wine), kanji, hingu, draksa, amlaka & bilva etc are useful in *Shwasa & Hikka*.⁵⁵

Pippali Churan with Ambala rasa when mix with madhu immediately relief *Hikka*. Similarly act the juices of amalaki & kapitha mixed with pippali & Honey.⁵⁶ Pippali powder 10 gm. Fried in oil & mixed with guda should be dissolved in Kulatha water & given to the patient. It can relieve spasm of cough caused by kapha.⁵⁷

Do's (Pathya)⁵⁸:

- Godhuma (wheat), Old rice, Mudga (green gram), Kulattha (Horse gram), Yava (barley), Patola (snake gourd)
- Use of Garlic, Turmeric, Ginger, Black pepper
- Luke warm water, Goat milk, Honey
- Respiratory exercise, Pranayama, Yoga

Don'ts (Apathya)⁵⁸:

- Heavy, cold diet, Masha (black gram), Deep fried items, Mustard leaves, Fish.
- Exposure to Cold & Humid atmosphere
- Sweets, Chilled water, Stored food items, Curd
- Suppression of natural urges
- Excessive physical exertion
- Exposure to Smoke, Dust and fumes, Pollutants and Pollens.

CONCLUSION:

This conceptual review has illuminated different fields from classical review to the latest information about the tamaka swasa. Bronchial asthma is the common respiratory disease which needs preventive and therapeutic approach. The present review helps to understand tamaka swasa according to Ayurvedic as well as modern perspective.

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